

Gender Differences in Problem Solving Observed in Logo Novices

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Abstract. Women are still underrepresented in particular fields, such as science, technology, engineering and math (STEM). In computer science, a particular aspect that is being investigated is the different approaches boys and girls take to programming tasks. Existing hypotheses state that boys are more inclined to unconventional solutions, while girls prefer to take a more structured approach. This study investigates the validity of this hypothesis, particularly in the context of novice programming in Logo using Turtle Graphics. Through a comparative analysis of the programs written by 42 children, a Chi-Square-Test shows no significant difference between boys and girls ($\chi^2 = 0.5046$ in terms of creativity and structurability); the Mann-Whitney U Test however shows a small gender bias in favor of males on the creativity variable ($p=0.06$). Our next steps consist in developing a more accurate measurement for structurability, given that we reached an interrater reliability score of only 0.237 for structuredness but 0.805 for creativity.

1 Introduction

As a central research topic, gender studies try to understand the inequalities, practices and interactions between men and women. Statistics show that in many areas, women's participation is underrepresented, in particular in STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) [12,8,1]. Some studies show gender differences in interest [10], confidence [11], and attitudes [13] in computer science. One particular difference lies in the way boys and girls proceed when they are programming. Several aspects point towards social factors that contribute to the difference: Korkmaz and Altun [9] found that the low participation of women in computer studies has a background of insecurity about the skills required for programming. Hanström [7] found that, in order to apply the method of trial and error, confidence in one's own abilities is essential.

Other results point towards cognitive differences that affect the low representation of women in computer science. Programming is an activity that requires several cognitive skills. Usually, emphasis is placed on: (1) logical thinking, (2) abstraction, and (3) creativity. Gender studies suggest that men outperform women in logic and abstraction skills as well as in solving unconventional

problem statements [2,3]. In contrast, when it comes to learning languages or solving conventional problem statements, women have been shown to outperform men [3,4,6].

In this work, we focus on the two indicators *structurability* and *creativity* and perform a qualitative study on whether novice Logo programmers show gender differences in terms of these two indicators.

2 Study

The primary objective of this work is to analyze whether there are gender-specific differences in terms of *creativity* and *structurability*. In order to answer this question, the authors planned an intervention with two groups of eleven and twelve year old students (N=49, 26 male, 23 female). Prior to the intervention, both classes were introduced to the basics of Logo programming (i.e, sequence, loops, procedures) for one school year with two hours every two weeks. The subsequent intervention lasted for one week, with 12 lessons per group.

After a short repetition on the previously-covered concepts, the students focused on the concepts, both framed within the topic of Logo animation. We worked with a textbook that proposes a sequence of predefined task [5]. After each day, the children's solutions were downloaded and stored for subsequent analysis. 7 children (4 boys and 3 girls) were excluded from the study since no data was saved. In order to rate the student's solutions on the spectrum of creativity and structurability, we defined the following point-rating:

Creativity:

- (2) The child uses concepts/approaches that have not been discussed in class. They develop custom tasks.
- (1) The child uses some commands/approaches that have not been discussed in class. They develop some programs without predefined tasks.
- (0) The child follows the approaches discussed in class. They rarely develop their own tasks.
- (-1) The child follows the approaches discussed in class. They follow the given tasks.
- (-2) The child exactly follows the approaches as per instruction. They strictly follow the given tasks.

Structurability:

- (2) The child consistently and purposefully uses loops, procedures and parameters to create short and concise solutions.
- (1) The child uses loops, procedures and parameters mostly purposefully.
- (0) Sometimes the child uses loops, procedures and parameters.
- (-1) Oftentimes the child does not use loops, procedures and parameters or they appear disorganized.
- (-2) The child does not use loops, procedures and parameter. If used, the concepts are not purposeful, hardly understandable and appear disorganized.

After conducting the intervention, the anonymized data was rated according to the above point-rating system in regard of creativity and structurability. Both

authors established an interrater agreement with regular discussions after every ten students with the aim to ensure consistency in the rating scheme. First, the data was anonymized in terms of gender information. Discrepancies existed predominantly on the structurability variable where only a fair agreement was reached ($\kappa = 0.237$). In contrast, the interrater reliability on the dimension of creativity yielded an almost perfect agreement ($\kappa = 0.805$).

3 Preliminary Results

The results of the interrater agreement is visualized below (see [Figure 1](#)). The figure on the left presents the results for all male participants; the figure in the middle shows the results for all female participants and the figure on the right shows all results combined. Each dot represents a group of children with a specific creativity-structurability score. The x-axis corresponds to the creativity score while the y-axis corresponds to the structurability score.

Fig. 1: The diagram illustrates the results for the 42 participants (left male participants, middle female participants, right all participants).

The score roughly clusters children in four categories (quadrants in the diagram): participants whose solutions are rated (i) creative and structured, (ii) creative and not structured, (iii) not creative and structured, (iv) not creative and not structured. Categories (i) and (ii) are reflected in the top and bottom right quadrants whereas categories (iii) and (iv) are reflected in the top and bottom left quadrants respectively. [Appendix A](#) presents some selected examples for children's programs that fall into these four categories.

The statistical chi-tests on a bias on gender were all insignificant ($\chi^2 = 0.5045$ for structuredness and $\chi^2 = 0.5045$ for creativity) on a level of $\alpha=5\%$. The one-sided Whitney-Mann U test however showed a p-value of 0.06 on the creativity variable, indicating that there is a slight gender bias in favor of male participants. Under the assumption that gender plays no role for creativity, only in 6/100 similar experiments, we would have found such a result or a more extreme one.

4 Future Work

We analyzed programs from 42 students with an average of 8 programs per student. In a second phase, we aim to gather and analyze data from more students and different schools to conduct a more quantitative analysis. Moreover, we aim to establish a more precise objective to measure structurability or separate the variable into smaller segments that can be measured more easily. Finally, we want to incorporate more variables (e.g., spatial orientation, abstraction, socio-cultural aspects) to get a better understanding of gender-impact.

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A Appendix

Listing 1.1: structured and creative

```

to cc :long :oban
  lt :oban
  repeat 90 [fd :long rt 1]
end

to petalo
  setpc random 16
  cc 3 0 rt 90 cc 3 0
end

to superflor
  repeat 5 [
    repeat 90/5 [
      petalo rt 1 petalo
    ]
    rt 72
  ]
end
    
```


a: structured and creative

Listing 1.2: not structured but creative

```

to jj
  repeat 8 [ fd 50 rt 45]
end

to hh
  jj repeat 3 [ fd 50 rt 45]
  fd 50 rt 90
end

to flor :g :h
  setpc 1 hh jj hh jj hh jj hh
  jj hh jj hh jj hh jj hh jj hh
  jj hh jj hh jj hh jj hh jj hh
  jj hh jj hh jj hh jj hh jj hh
  jj hh jj hh jj rt :g fd:h
  rt 180 rt :g rt 45 fd :h
  setpc 2 fd 200 fd :h
  repeat 360 [fd 1 rt 1 ]
end
    
```


b: not structured but creative

Listing 1.3: structured but not creative

```
to stairs :gr :anz
  repeat :gr [
    quad :anz
    fd :anz rt 90
    fd :anz lt 90
  ]
end
```


a: structured but not creative

Listing 1.4: not structured not creative

```
to star8
  repeat 8 [
    fd 100 bk 100 rt 45
    fd 100 bk 100 lt 45
  ]
end
```


b: not structured and not creative